

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

Technical Report

The Alan Turing Institute: Carbon
emissions from computing

Rosie Wood

March 2026

Report number 10

© The Alan Turing Institute 2026

This work is licensed under Creative Commons licence CC BY-SA 4.0.

To view a copy of this licence, visit

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

The Alan Turing Institute is a charity incorporated and registered in England and Wales with company number 09512457 and charity number 1162533 whose registered office is at British Library, 96 Euston Road, London, England, NW1 2DB, United Kingdom.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19237594>

1 Introduction

In 2024, data centres consumed around 1.5 % of the world’s total electricity and accounted for around 180 MtCO₂e (0.3 % of global greenhouse gas emissions) [1, 2]. Electricity consumption by data centres is forecast to more than double by 2030, largely driven by AI [1].

In this work, we estimate the greenhouse gas emissions from the Turing’s use of its main compute resources (Microsoft Azure, Baskerville High Performance Computing system (HPC) and GitHub Actions) and identify areas in which we could reduce these emissions. Our results are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of operational and embodied emissions from Azure, Baskerville and GitHub Actions between September 2024–August 2025.

Compute resource	Electricity / kWh	Emissions / tCO ₂ e		
		Operational	Embodied	Total
Microsoft Azure	—	0 [†]	2.9	2.9
Baskerville (CHP)	83 300	25	6	31
GitHub Actions	380 [‡]	0 [†]	0.1	0.1

[†] Market-based operational emissions; location-based emissions cannot be calculated (see Section 3).

[‡] Extrapolated from six months of data (March–August 2025).

To help put these emissions from computing into perspective it can be helpful to compare against carbon emissions from other sources on similar scales:

- In the UK in 2022, per-capita emissions were approximately 5 tCO₂e per year [3].
- A flight from London to New York emits approximately 1 tCO₂e per passenger [4].

The remainder of this report is structured as follows. Section 2 provides background on emissions scopes and methodology. Section 3 covers emissions from Microsoft Azure, Section 4 covers emissions from Baskerville HPC and Section 5 covers emissions from GitHub Actions. Finally, we summarise our findings and outline potential areas for reducing emissions.

2 Background

Emissions are categorised as one of three scopes [5]:

Scope 1 covers emissions from sources that an organisation owns or controls directly.

Scope 2 are emissions that a company causes indirectly and come from where the energy it purchases and uses is produced. Scope 2 emissions can be calculated in one of two ways:

- Market-based Scope 2 emissions reflect those from electricity that companies have purposefully chosen (*e.g.*, if they have chosen a fully renewable tariff, market-based Scope 2 emissions will be zero).
- Location-based Scope 2 emissions reflect the average emissions intensity of grids on which energy consumption occurs.

Scope 3 encompasses emissions that are not produced by the company itself and are not the result of activities from assets owned or controlled by them, but by those that it is indirectly responsible for up and down its value chain.

Emissions from compute broadly come from one of two sources: emissions from energy consumption when running the hardware (known as operational emissions) and embodied emissions from manufacturing, transporting and disposing of the hardware. For the compute provider (*e.g.*, Azure or an HPC host organisation), operational emissions correspond to Scope 1 (on-site fuel use) and Scope 2 (purchased electricity), while embodied emissions fall under Scope 3 (upstream/downstream supply chain). For the Turing, the vast majority of our emissions from computing are classed as Scope 3 since in most cases we do not own the hardware we run on nor do we pay directly for the electricity that powers it. Emissions from Turing-owned hardware (*e.g.*, laptops, commercial GPUs and Raspberry Pis) are not covered in this report, though these may become increasingly significant with the growing use of locally-run LLMs.

To calculate operational emissions, the carbon emissions from electricity use are calculated by multiplying energy consumption by the carbon intensity of that energy, where carbon intensity is a measure of the carbon emissions per kWh of electricity consumed. This is a relatively simple calculation and makes it straightforward to estimate operational emissions provided that energy consumption and carbon intensity are known. Embodied emissions, however, are far more complicated to calculate since they require upstream data from vendors, such as manufacturing and transportation emissions, and a life-cycle assessment.

3 Microsoft Azure

Microsoft Azure has its own carbon optimisation and emission tracking dashboard which make it possible to view emissions resulting from the Turing's Azure usage.

Azure users can access this themselves and see data related to Azure subscriptions they are part of. An example screenshot is shown in Figure 1 (note that this shows data for different dates than discussed below).

Figure 1: Azure Carbon Optimisation dashboard

The Azure emissions dashboard breaks down emissions by month and by scope. Here, Scope 1 emissions refer to Microsoft’s Scope 1 emissions (*e.g.*, from their own power plants), Scope 2 emissions refer to Microsoft’s Scope 2 emissions (*e.g.*, from energy they buy from the grid) and Scope 3 emissions refer to Microsoft’s Scope 3 emissions (*e.g.*, from the hardware they purchase).

Figure 2 shows the data for the past year (September 2024–August 2025). From this, we see the majority of the Turing’s Azure emissions come from Microsoft’s Scope 3 emissions, with a small contribution from Microsoft’s Scope 1 emissions (most likely back-up power generation). Over this period, the Turing’s total emissions from Azure were just 2.9 tCO₂e.

This number is surprisingly low because Scope 2 emissions, which we would expect to be the biggest contributor to Azure emissions, are reported as zero. That is because Microsoft only report market-based Scope 2 emissions, which reflect the carbon intensity of the specific energy tariff they have chosen rather than the grid average (as described in Section 2), and since Microsoft uses renewable energy tariffs [6]; the carbon intensity of their energy is zero. Since there is no information on our energy usage, it is impossible to calculate location-based Scope 2 emissions.

Figure 2: Azure monthly emissions (September 2024–August 2025)

4 Baskerville

Baskerville is by far the most widely used HPC at the Turing due to our institutional allocation which makes it particularly easy for Turing projects to access and utilise Baskerville HPC. Consequently, it is also our biggest source of compute emissions.

Baskerville is hosted by the University of Birmingham which, based on information from the Baskerville team, uses a gas powered combined heat and power (CHP) plant to power its campus. Consequently, Baskerville’s operational emissions should be calculated using the carbon intensity of this CHP plant instead of that of the national grid. There is limited information about emissions from Birmingham’s CHP plant, but the University of Edinburgh reported its CHP plant emissions had a carbon intensity of 366 gCO₂e/kWh [7]—almost three times higher than the UK national average of 124 gCO₂e/kWh [8] in 2024. Noussan *et al.* also found similar values, suggesting an annual average in the range 270 to 304 gCO₂e/kWh [9]. We have therefore used a value of 300 gCO₂e/kWh to represent the estimated carbon intensity of the University of Birmingham’s CHP plant.

As Turing admins for Baskerville, we are able to access an admin portal to download usage data for the whole Turing across all time. This data contains somewhat limited information for each job, but includes run times, requested resources and submission dates. This is enough information to be able to create a rough estimate for operational emissions originating from the Turing’s usage of Baskerville.

The code in the `turing_emissions` repository¹ shows a simple way of calculating operational emissions from our Baskerville usage. This is done using the formula shown in Equation (1) where E_{gpu} , E_{cpu} and E_{mem} are the energy used by the GPUs, CPUs and memory, respectively, PUE is the power usage effectiveness of

¹https://github.com/rwood-97/turing_emissions/tree/main

the HPC and CI is the carbon intensity at the time of that energy usage. Energy is calculated using equation (2) where $E_{\text{component}}$ is the energy used by the component (GPU, CPU or memory), $t_{\text{component}}$ is the time that component is in use for and $P_{\text{component}}$ is the power draw of that component. For both GPU and CPU, power draw can be taken as the Thermal Design Power (TDP) of the component, as reported by the manufacturer, and for memory, power draw can be taken as a constant power draw of 0.3725 W GB^{-1} of requested memory [10].

$$E_{\text{operational}} = (E_{\text{gpu}} + E_{\text{cpu}} + E_{\text{mem}}) \times \text{PUE} \times \text{CI} \quad (1)$$

$$E_{\text{component}} = t_{\text{component}} \times P_{\text{component}} \quad (2)$$

Figure 3 shows the calculated energy usage of Turing’s Baskerville jobs since mid-2021 (when the Turing first gained pilot access to Baskerville), broken down by year and component. Here we see that energy consumption is dominated by GPU and CPU usage whilst memory accounts for a comparatively smaller fraction.

Although these calculated energy values should only be taken as estimates due to large errors in the data, they are accurate enough to give a sense of our energy usage over the years. Errors originate from the following sources:

- The energy values shown reflect the energy needed to operate GPUs, CPUs and memory, as well as the overheads of the Baskerville HPC facility. However, they do not take into account additional overheads, such as energy needed to operate interconnect switches, storage, coolant systems, etc. For ARCHER2, the UK National Supercomputing Service hosted by EPCC at the University of Edinburgh, these overheads account for around 15 % power draw [11] and for Isambard-AI, an AI-optimised HPC and part of the UK’s AI Research Resource, these overheads account for around 8 % of operational emissions [12]. This would mean the values are underestimating the energy requirements for running Baskerville.
- The energy values shown are calculated using the thermal design power (TDP) values provided by NVIDIA for their GPUs and therefore assume 100 % GPU power usage. However, GPU utilisation is often less than 100 % when running GPU jobs on HPC [13] and, in fact, according to the Baskerville team, some of the Baskerville GPUs are power capped. This would mean the values are overestimating the energy requirements when using Baskerville GPUs.

As per Equation (1), energy values per job are multiplied by carbon intensity at runtime to calculate carbon emissions. Two approaches to this are: using the carbon intensity of the University of Birmingham’s CHP plant ($300 \text{ gCO}_2\text{e/kWh}$), or, using the carbon intensity of the national grid. For the latter, since carbon intensity

Figure 3: Baskerville energy usage per year, broken down by component (August 2021–August 2025)

values fluctuate throughout the day and throughout the year, different averaging approaches yield different emissions values. Three approaches to averaging carbon intensity are: 1. Taking a yearly average (for example, in 2024 the UK average carbon intensity was 124 gCO₂e/kWh [8]); 2. Taking a daily average using the Carbon Intensity API²; and 3. Taking an hourly average, again using the Carbon Intensity API.

The `run_baskerville_emissions` notebook³ shows the results under each of these different approaches. Using the CHP plant approach, the Turing’s operational emissions over its entire use of Baskerville were 89.2 tCO₂e and its operational emissions in the past year (September 2024–August 2025) were 25.0 tCO₂e. Using the national grid approach, with a yearly average carbon intensity of 124 gCO₂e/kWh, the Turing’s operational emissions over its entire use of Baskerville were 36.9 tCO₂e and its operational emissions in the past year (September 2024–August 2025) were 10.3 tCO₂e. This is approximately 2.4 (300/124) times lower than using the CHP plant approach. This lower carbon intensity reflects the fact that the national grid draws from a mix of sources — including renewables and nuclear, which have near-zero carbon intensities — whereas the CHP plant runs purely on gas. Notably, even when using the national grid approach, our operational emissions from Baskerville usage are significantly higher than from our entire Azure usage (operational plus embodied emissions).

Using the national grid approach with daily average CIs, the Turing’s operational emissions over its entire use of Baskerville were 48.5 tCO₂e and its operational emissions in the past year were 10.9 tCO₂e. Using this approach, our overall emissions were higher but our emissions for the past year were lower. These

²<https://carbon-intensity.github.io/api-definitions/#carbon-intensity-api-v2-0-0>

³https://github.com/rwood-97/turing_emissions/blob/main/run_baskerville_emissions.ipynb

variations are due to a reduction in grid carbon intensity over time as more renewables are added to the national grid, meaning historical CIs were higher than 124 gCO₂e/kWh but this current year’s average carbon intensity is lower.

A number of open source tools for measuring operational emissions from HPC are available on GitHub [14, 12]. GRACE-HPC, developed by Elliot Ayliffe and the Bristol Centre for SuperComputing (BriCS) team [12], is one example. Generally, these tools use the slurm `sacct`⁴ command (or the non-slurm equivalent of this command if an alternative job scheduler is being used) to gather information about completed jobs and calculates their carbon emissions based on the carbon intensity at the job’s run time. However, due to privacy restrictions, Baskerville users are only able to see information about their own jobs using `sacct`. This is true even for Turing admins and so instead of running GRACE-HPC directly on Baskerville, `sacct` data for the Turing’s usage of Baskerville was kindly provided directly by the Baskerville team. The code was adapted to use this pre-saved data as input.⁵

Running GRACE-HPC on the provided data showed that the Turing’s operational emissions were approximately 11.2 tCO₂e from its usage of Baskerville in the past year (September 2024–August 2025). Notably, this is around 25 % higher than calculated using daily average CIs, though it is unclear where these differences arise. This aligns with the numbers seen when using the daily averaging approach, showing that approximating with a daily average carbon intensity is a reasonable choice.

Figure 4 shows how the Turing’s usage of Baskerville and the UK average carbon intensity vary throughout the day. From this, we see that on average the Turing has the highest number of jobs running between 11 am and 5 pm. Interestingly, when compared against the UK average carbon intensity, we see that our jobs are generally being run when carbon intensity is lowest.

GRACE-HPC also highlights other data from our Baskerville usage. For example, the Turing ran 48 099 jobs over the course of the last year, summing to 138 073 GPU h. However, around half (48.9 %) of those finished with a non-zero exit code. This indicates that these jobs did not run to completion. This could mean that jobs were interrupted due to an error or due to time constraints and therefore there is potential for lost results and wasted energy. According to GRACE-HPC, these jobs account for approximately 7.1 tCO₂e—over half of the Turing’s Baskerville emissions. Reducing the number of these jobs would significantly reduce our operational emissions from HPC use. This could be achieved by offering more training for new HPC users, guidance on best practices when submitting jobs to

⁴<https://slurm.schedmd.com/sacct.html>

⁵Specifically, to save time and reduce the number of API calls, some caching was added and the carbon intensity averaging adjusted to use hourly averages rather than exact carbon intensity values on a job-by-job basis. See pull requests #1 (<https://github.com/Elliot-Ayliffe/GRACE-HPC/pull/1>), #2 (<https://github.com/Elliot-Ayliffe/GRACE-HPC/pull/2>) and #3 (<https://github.com/Elliot-Ayliffe/GRACE-HPC/pull/3>).

Figure 4: UK average carbon intensity and average number of Baskerville jobs running at each hour of the day (September 2024–August 2025).

HPC and raising awareness of the emissions from failed jobs.

A full comparison between the four methods is shown in Table 2. Clearly, the biggest influence on the operational emissions from our Baskerville usage is the provider of the electricity with less influence coming from the averaging method. Since the source of electricity for Baskerville HPC is a CHP plant, these numbers from the CHP plant approach are likely the best estimate of the four methods. Due to the errors in the energy estimates (mentioned above) and variations in the carbon intensity values, these operational emissions values should still only be taken as rough estimates.

Approach	Averaging method	Emissions / tCO _{2e}	
		All time	Year to date
CHP plant	Yearly	89.2	25.0
National Grid	Yearly	36.9	10.3
National Grid	Daily	48.5	10.9
National Grid	Hourly	—	11.2

Table 2: Comparison of the different methods for calculating operational emissions from HPC.

4.0.1 Emissions rate

Since we don't necessarily want to reduce our usage of HPC, it's useful instead to think of emissions as a rate per functional unit. For example, per GPUh, per useful output or, for AI workloads, per token. In the past year, the Turing ran jobs summing to 138 073 GPU h and so our emissions rate is 81.3 gCO₂e/GPU h (using the GPUh and emissions values reported by GRACE-HPC). Methods of improving this rate would include making code more efficient by reducing idle times or using more efficient algorithms, ensuring requested resources are correct for the workload (*e.g.*, ensuring the optimal number of GPUs/nodes/memory) and running jobs at times where carbon intensity is lower (also known as carbon aware scheduling). For the latter, this is only a viable approach if a) Baskerville GPU's are being used at less than 100 % capacity and b) it was a system-wide approach, i.e. there are no rebound effects. A similar approach could be taken for AI workloads using rate per token.

4.0.2 Embodied emissions

Recent work focused on estimating the embodied emissions of HPCs from the Top500 list⁶ [15] estimated Baskerville's embodied emissions to be 381 tCO₂e. This value was calculated using EasyC [16], a tool which estimates embodied carbon emissions based on a only few simple parameters – the number of compute units, storage capacity and memory capacity.

To verify this number, we can compare against other HPCs for which in-depth embodied emissions analyses have been undertaken. For example, the embodied emissions from Isambard-AI (Phase 2), a GPU-based HPC, is estimated to be 8184 tCO₂e [17]. Isambard-AI (Phase 2) is made up of 1320 nodes with GH200 chips. Each GH200 chip has one Grace CPU and one H100 GPU. There are four GH200 chips per node and 72 cores per GPU. Isambard-AI also has 1056 30.72 TB NVMe SSDs. [18] In comparison, the Baskerville system is made up of 48 nodes with A100 GPUs and two nodes with H100 GPUs. For both A100 and H100 nodes, there are four GPUs per node and 36 cores per GPU. Baskerville also has 48 7.68 TB SSDs. From these system specifications, we see Isambard-AI has 26× more compute nodes than Baskerville. A naive estimate for the embodied emissions of Baskerville would therefore be around 310 tCO₂e (8184/26). However, this does not account for the different GPUs types, number of CPUs per node or SSD capacities. Nevertheless, this supports the idea that embodied emissions for Baskerville HPC should be on the order of 300 tCO₂e.

Embodied emissions can be converted to embodied emissions per unit time such that embodied emissions can be apportioned to the different users of these HPC systems based upon their usage. For Isambard-AI, using an estimated 6 year service

⁶<https://top500.org/lists/top500/>

lifetime, embodied emissions are estimated to be 0.114 kgCO₂e per node hour [17, 19]. Since Baskerville has been running since 2021 and is due to be shut down in 2026, its service lifetime is 5 years. This gives an estimated embodied emissions per unit time of 0.174 kgCO₂e per node hour or 0.043 kgCO₂e GPU h⁻¹. Given our usage over the past year of 138 073 GPU h, the Turing’s share of embodied emissions from our Baskerville usage is 6 tCO₂e in the past year. Comparing this against the values in Table 2, this suggests that over the past year operational emissions outweighed embodied emissions for Baskerville HPC. This means that pushing for Baskerville to be powered by renewable electricity, or moving to a greener HPC, would be the most effective method of reducing our emissions from compute. Notably, since embodied emissions are fixed at the point of manufacture, embodied emissions generally dominate over operational emissions in newer HPCs. Thus, maximising HPC utilisation is the most carbon-efficient way to spread those costs across useful work.

5 GitHub Actions

Since GitHub uses Azure virtual machines (VMs) to run GitHub Actions workflows, and we know that Azure uses renewable electricity with a carbon intensity of zero, the most likely value for the Turing’s operational emissions from GitHub actions is zero. Our embodied emissions are more difficult to estimate, but are likely to be low, since GitHub actions uses small virtual machines with only a few CPUs. Optimising our use of GitHub actions is therefore not likely to impact our overall emissions from compute.

5.1 Market-based emissions

For sake of argument, it is possible to calculate the Turing’s emissions from GitHub Actions using the market-based approach. The Turing’s GitHub organisation⁷ ran 3340 hours of GitHub Actions in the past six months (March 2025–September 2025). To estimate the operation emissions from this work, we must know a) the energy consumption and b) the carbon intensity of the energy consumed.

GitHub provide some information about the default runners used when a GitHub Actions workflow is triggered, including information about the number of CPUs and RAM on the VM [20]. This helps us understand what compute resources are being used and thus estimate their energy consumption. To understand the carbon intensity of the energy consumed, we need to know where this energy is coming from. I created a support request to GitHub to ask about the location of these runners and got the following response: “Standard and larger GitHub-hosted

⁷<https://github.com/alan-turing-institute>

runners are all hosted in North America (primarily in the United States, and occasionally Canada).” Together, this information can be used to work out the approximate operational emissions from the Turing’s use of GitHub actions using the Green Algorithms calculator [10].

In the previous six months, a rough estimate for our operational emissions related to GitHub actions runners is 50 kgCO₂e. This was calculated using the Green Algorithms calculator and the following settings: 3340 hours of runtime, four CPUs, 7 GB memory and setting the Azure region as North Central US. Assuming this value is representative, this equates to just 100 kgCO₂e for the year - negligible compared to our Azure and HPC emissions and confirms that optimising GitHub Actions usage is unlikely to significantly affect our overall compute-related emissions.

6 Conclusion

This report explores three different sources of computing emissions from the Turing: Microsoft Azure, Baskerville HPC and GitHub Actions. The Turing’s emissions from these compute resources are summarised in Table 1. In total, our use of these resources accounted for around 34 tCO₂e emissions in the past year. This is equivalent to just under seven times the average UK per-capita emissions or around 35 passengers on a transatlantic flight to New York. More than anything, this demonstrates the huge emissions impact of flying.

Notably, the majority of the Turing’s compute emissions came from Baskerville HPC, a GPU-based machine where the bulk of our workloads are AI-focused. This highlights the large impact of AI’s emissions compared to other computing workloads and suggests contributing to research into greener AI technologies would be an effective route to reducing the Turing’s emissions whilst also having a wider impact.

Reducing emissions from Baskerville is currently the largest opportunity for reducing our emissions, the easiest way of doing this would be to encourage the Baskerville team to put Baskerville on a renewable electricity tariff. An alternative approach, especially in light of Baskerville’s end of life in 2026, would be to encourage Turing projects to move to greener HPCs such as those listed in the Green500 [21]. Other potential avenues for reducing the Turing’s emissions from Baskerville usage, and which also apply to usage of other HPCs, include reducing the number of failed jobs — for example, by providing more training or guidance for HPC users — and improving the efficiency of jobs by optimising the compute resources requested or using more energy efficient algorithms.

Other sources of emissions not covered in this report due to lack of data include other UK HPCs which the Turing makes use of (Isambard-AI and Dawn), Turing-owned hardware (laptops, commercial GPUs and Pi’s) and collaborators’

hardware.

References

- [1] *IEA - Energy and AI*. <https://www.iea.org/reports/energy-and-ai>. Accessed 2025-10-22.
- [2] *UNEP Emissions Gap Report 2025*. <https://www.unep.org/resources/emissions-gap-report-2025>. Accessed 2026-03-23.
- [3] *IEA - United Kingdom Emissions*. <https://www.iea.org/countries/united-kingdom/emissions>. Accessed 2025-10-22.
- [4] *CO₂ Flight Calculator*. https://co2.myclimate.org/en/flight_calculators/new. Accessed 2025-10-24.
- [5] *What are scope 1, 2 and 3 carbon emissions?* <https://www.nationalgrid.com/stories/energy-explained/what-are-scope-1-2-3-carbon-emissions>. Accessed 2025-10-12.
- [6] *Troubleshooting Carbon optimization in Azure*. <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/carbon-optimization/troubleshooting#all-or-most-scope-2-emissions-are-zero>. Accessed 2025-10-12.
- [7] *The case for immediately powering down the CHP plant in Kings Buildings, installing heat pumps, and securing a power purchase agreement for 100% renewable electricity*. <https://webhomes.maths.ed.ac.uk/~djordan/CHP-discussion.pdf>. Accessed 2025-10-22.
- [8] *Britain's Electricity Explained: 2024 Review*. <https://www.neso.energy/news/britains-electricity-explained-2024-review>. Accessed 2025-10-22.
- [9] Michel Noussan et al. "Hourly electricity CO₂ intensity profiles based on the real operation of large-scale natural gas combined cycle cogeneration plants". In: *Energy* 312 (2024), p. 133424. ISSN: 0360-5442. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.133424>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544224032006>.
- [10] Loïc Lannelongue, Jason Grealey, and Michael Inouye. "Green Algorithms: Quantifying the Carbon Footprint of Computation". In: *Advanced Science* 8.12 (2021), p. 2100707. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/adv.202100707>. eprint: <https://advanced.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/adv.202100707>. URL: <https://advanced.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/adv.202100707>.
- [11] *ARCHER₂ - Energy use and Emissions*. <https://docs.archer2.ac.uk/user-guide/energy/#scope-2-emissions>. Accessed 2025-10-22.

- [12] *GRACE-HPC*. <https://github.com/Ellyot-Ayliffe/GRACE-HPC>. Accessed 2025-10-22.
- [13] Efe Sencan et al. “Analyzing GPU Utilization in HPC Workloads: Insights from Large-Scale Systems”. In: *Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing 2025: The Power of Collaboration*. PEARC ’25. Association for Computing Machinery, 2025. ISBN: 9798400713989. DOI: 10.1145/3708035.3736010. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3708035.3736010>.
- [14] *GreenAlgorithms4HPC*. <https://github.com/GreenAlgorithms/GreenAlgorithms4HPC>. Accessed 2025-10-22.
- [15] Varsha Rao and Andrew A. Chien. “Modeling the Carbon Footprint of HPC: The Top 500 and EasyC”. In: *Proceedings of the SC ’25 Workshops of the International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis*. SC Workshops ’25. ACM, Nov. 2025, pp. 2032–2040. DOI: 10.1145/3731599.3767567. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3731599.3767567>.
- [16] Varsha Rao and Andrew A. Chien. “EasyC: Practical Carbon-Emissions Estimates for Research Computing Systems”. In: *Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing 2025: The Power of Collaboration*. PEARC ’25. Association for Computing Machinery, 2025. ISBN: 9798400713989. DOI: 10.1145/3708035.3736052. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3708035.3736052>.
- [17] *Isambard Emissions Analysis*. <https://github.com/Ellyot-Ayliffe/Isambard-Emissions-Analysis>. Accessed 2025-10-27.
- [18] Simon McIntosh-Smith, Sadaf Alam, and Christopher Woods. “Isambard-AI: a leadership-class supercomputer optimised specifically for Artificial Intelligence”. In: *Proceedings of the Cray User Group*. CUG ’24. Association for Computing Machinery, 2025, pp. 44–54. ISBN: 9798400713286. DOI: 10.1145/3725789.3725794. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3725789.3725794>.
- [19] *ARCHER2 - Environmental Sustainability*. <https://www.archer2.ac.uk/community/sustainability/>. Accessed 2025-10-22.
- [20] *GitHub-hosted runners reference*. <https://docs.github.com/en/actions/reference/runners/github-hosted-runners>. Accessed 2025-10-12.
- [21] *June 2025 - GREEN500*. <https://top500.org/lists/green500/2025/06/>. Accessed 2025-10-27.